

METHODOLOGY MODEL FOR IMPROVING THE ETHNO- PEDAGOGICAL CULTURE OF THE FUTURE MUSIC TEACHER

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Annotation: This study focused on the model of methods used to improve the ethnopedagogical culture of future music teachers. Various pedagogical conditions and recommendations are included in the improvement of ethnopedagogical culture, and the model of methodical methods used in improving the ethnopedagogical culture of undergraduate music education students is highlighted.

Keywords: Music, pedagogy, model, ethnopedagogy, education, music creation, criterion, method, competition, festival, motive, cognitive, compensation, methodology.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotni bajarishda bo'lajak musiqa o'qituvchilarining etnopedagogik madaniyatini takomillashtirish qo'llanilgan metodlar modeliga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Etnopedagogik madaniyatini takomillashtirishda turli pedagogik shart-sharoitlar, tavsiyalar o'rin olgan bo'lib, musiqa ta'limi bakalavriat ta'limi yo'nalishi talabalarining etnopedagogik madaniyatini takomillashtirishda qo'llanilgan metodik usullar modeli yoritilgan.

Tayanch iboralar: Musiqa, pedagogika, model, etnopedagogika, ta'lim, musiqa ijodi, mezon, usul, tanlov, festival, motiv, kognitiv.kompentatsiya, metodika.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании основное внимание уделяется модели методов, используемых для повышения этнопедагогической культуры будущих учителей музыки. В процесс повышения этнопедагогической культуры включены различные педагогические условия и рекомендации, а также выделена модель методических приемов, используемых при повышении этнопедагогической культуры студентов бакалавриата музыкального образования.

Ключевые слова: Музыка, педагогика, модель, этнопедагогика, образование, музыкальное творчество, критерий, метод, конкуренция, праздник, мотив, когнитивная компенсация, методология.

In the method of improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of the future music teacher, we paid attention to the professional and pedagogical aspects of their professional performance. This form of the identified problem was related

to the fact that the professional culture of the future music teacher finds its direct expression in the ability to organize activities that achieve a pedagogical result with the help of created artistic objects. That is, the artistic, instrumental or singing performance ability when performing musical works (or their fragments) is an attributive quality of the future music teacher's ethno-pedagogical culture.

According to the concept of artistic activity, the main types of human activity are an organic combination of cognitive, value-oriented, communicative and transformative. It follows that the ability of artistic activity includes the ability to know, evaluate, communicate and create. Based on this point of view and taking into account the performance "embeddedness" of the student in music pedagogy in the educational process, the ethnopedagogical culture of the future music teacher is to create, evaluate, know and considered as an integral ability to communicate.

Music education as an educational field is the basis of the pedagogic unit. Understanding the ethno-pedagogical culture of the future music teacher in this way, it is impossible to fully ensure the process of its formation within the framework of the existing discrete-disciplinary system of professional training of students of music education of higher educational institutions. If the future music student's personal, professional, ethno-pedagogical and social development is built as a system that ensures the mastery of performance skills from the initial level, then in the process of playing a musical instrument, the future music teacher's ethno-pedagogical culture improvement we assumed that the level can be reached. To study the possibilities of turning this assumption into reality, we turn to the modeling method. At the same time, we believe that this method is a general scientific method of scientific research and allows combining empirical and theory in the study of pedagogical phenomena. That is, in the process of learning a pedagogical object, it is necessary to take into account the combination of experience with the construction of logical structures and scientific abstractions. It is an effective tool for designing instruction to build a model.

The main concept of the modeling method is the model. One of its most common definitions is as follows: "A model is a mentally represented or materially realized system that can replace the object of study by representing or reproducing it, therefore study provides new information about this object.

The definition given by (A.N. Dakhin) is important in building a methodology model for improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of a future

music teacher. For example, "A model is an artificially created object in the form of a scheme, physical structures, symbolic forms and formulas, which are similar to the object (or phenomenon) being studied, and the structure of this object , shows and reproduces the relationships between properties, relationships, and elements in a simpler and coarser form. The model is based on the idea of overcoming the tendency of highly specialized direction by integrating the psychological-pedagogical aspects of musical performance and ethno-pedagogical training in the teaching of performance sciences at the pedagogical university. The specificity of the ethno-pedagogical activity of future music teachers constitutes a certain type of professional thinking, however, without taking into account the contradiction that is not always taken into account, classes are organized in group, collective, ensemble, individual forms and Lajak depends on the "public" nature of the music teacher's activity. Rather, the "development process of the person" has both social and individual importance, and both sides are closely related.

The need to develop such integrative and creative abilities of students determined the third direction of building the process of their performing and musical literacy activities with the aim of improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of the future music teacher. The indicated position is reflected in the structural-functional model for the formation of professional and ethno-pedagogical culture of future music teachers in the course of musical and singing performance training and determines its multi-level structure expressed in blocks: tentatively targeted, theoretically methodological , pedagogical conditions, content-procedural, criteria-evaluated.

Thus, the approximate-target block performs the functions of target setting and forecasting. Goal setting includes setting goals and tasks related to achieving them. The predictive function is to direct the learning process to the expected result. The content, forms and methods of the tentative-objective block, as well as the purpose of the theoretical and methodological block, which performs a regulatory function in connection with the activities of the subjects of the design process. This block is represented by a set of methodological approaches to the goal of the process being modeled. Note that, in its most general form, the category of approach indicates the invariant basis chosen for the analysis and design of any phenomenon. The term "approach to learning" currently does not have an unambiguous interpretation. This concept can act as a carrier of social consciousness, as a category of worldview that reflects the social relations of educational subjects. It also describes the global and

systematic organization of the educational process. , including all its components and, first of all, the subjects of pedagogical interaction themselves. systematic, integrative, personal activity, competence-based and cultural approaches to improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of the music teacher could be considered "optimal".

The success of the process of designing the methodology for improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of the future music teacher is largely determined by the formation of the system of professional values among the future music teachers. Therefore, when developing the model, we initially considered the orientation of worldview guidelines, which determine the state of professional culture of students as its basis. Undergraduate instrumental and vocal performance and music literacy activities require professional training and the selection and high mastery of a wide repertoire of works in nearly every style and genre that students should be familiar with. Such a need for the diversity of the repertoire affects the performance and creative abilities of future music students, such as musical and figurative perception, understanding of music, listening, hearing, artistic figurative thinking, musical and figurative memory, sensorimotor qualities of hands, emotional response to performance. implies disclosure.

The ability of individual creative interpretation also determined the second direction of this designed process - "mastering of performance technologies by students as a combination of all methods and tools, actions and operations, skills and abilities of the most diverse content, with the help of which music o "the teacher, taking into account the external and internal conditions (factors), in one way or another manages the performance process, more broadly - with his own artistic and creative activity". It is necessary to form a holistic vision of pedagogical performance of undergraduate students as a part of professional and ethno-pedagogical activity as a system. [1]

In the development of the model, the connection between theoretical rules and pedagogical practice is built on the basis of the principles that reflect the main laws of the programmed process - the dependence of the educational process on the needs of society and the individual; the dependence of teaching on the individual characteristics of the student; showed the interdependence of the goals, tasks, content, methods, forms and results of the educational process. The humanistic direction of the pedagogical process is one of the main principles as the leading principle of education, which expresses the need for a harmonious unity of society and individual goals. Adherence to this principle improves not

only the student, but also the necessary competencies in accordance with the state educational standard and qualification requirements of the music education field of study.

The method of improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of the future music teacher always has a quality feature, both at the social and personal levels. That is, it was determined by the "high or low" formula. The level of ethno-pedagogical culture of a student is determined by the degree to which he fulfills the role of an educator and teacher. The latter is connected with a number of factors, such as the life experience of the scientist, human wisdom of the teacher, the amount of knowledge he has, skills and abilities to transfer his knowledge. It should be noted that in the process of the distribution of levels and the clear placement of emphasis in their understanding, the future music teacher's ethno-pedagogical culture is determined by progressive movement towards the improvement of the goal. Thus, we stopped at three levels in the research: low (critical), medium (basic), high (optimal). Indicators at this criterion level will be considered in more detail in the next section of our study. [2]

The content and characteristics of the organization of the modeled process reveal the content-procedural block, thereby performing formative, organizational and motivating functions. The core of the content part is the characteristics of the components of the ethno-pedagogical culture of the future music teacher (the system of professional and value orientations; the system of knowledge, skills and abilities related to instrumental and choral performance activities in the context) is determined. general music education; general professional and special competitions; professional and personal qualities of a future music teacher; the need for continuous self-development and self-improvement in professional activity, instrumental performance is an integral part of it. The content component includes the pedagogical content of musical-theoretical sciences, as well as the implementation of a special course "Instrumental and singing performance of the future music teacher and musical literacy activities".

The logical basis of the goal of the model is the social order of training a socially active, highly professional, creatively oriented future music teacher, and the generalized semantic characteristic of this order is the ethnopedagogical culture of students, which is a set of directed, creative, effective professional and pedagogical activities. The expediency and effectiveness of the modeled process was determined by the presence of - approximate - target, theoretical -

methodological, pedagogical conditions, content - procedural and criterion-evaluation relations between the model blocks.

Figure 1. Methodology model for improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of the future music teacher

It included target, conceptual, process and result-evaluation components of the organizational-structural model. These are:

Target component. The structure of the model elements is the main component of the studied process, the goal is to improve the ethno-pedagogical culture of the future music teacher. [3] The implementation of this goal certainly has its own regulatory and legal basis, and the necessary tasks are carried out within the framework of the tasks defined in the regulatory and legal documents. Based on the regulatory and legal bases defined as a social necessity in the targeted component, it is directed to the improvement of teaching methods by effectively organizing the educational activities of students.

Organizational-structural component. There are a number of methods for improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of a future music teacher - competence, person-oriented, integrative, systematic-activity approaches and flexibility, connection with practice, connection with natural and social values, continuation of ethno-pedagogical traditions. implies the implementation based on the principles and the use of a number of methods in improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of the future music teacher.

Component on educational and methodical activity. Based on the concept [4], which expresses the use of form, content, tools and methods in a logical sequence between the set goal and the achieved result, students' it was shown that it creates an opportunity to develop the competence of working with information in connection with ethno-pedagogical culture. It is known that any skills are formed only in conditions that allow it. The factor that forms competences and makes them look solid is the continuous, systematic organization of the process of improving basic competences. This means regularity, continuity, and serves to ensure the integrity of the education and upbringing process, sequence and regularity in the improvement of ethno-pedagogical culture [5].

An important structural unit of the model is a set of teaching methods aimed at improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of the future music teacher. In the science of pedagogy, the concept of "educational method" has been given different definitions, but most of the researchers in their definitions start from understanding it as a method of organizing educational activities. It is appropriate to interpret the teaching method as an ordered method of joint activity of teachers and students aimed at solving educational problems. The choice of teaching methods is governed by the way of mastering its purpose and content and the nature of interaction between the subjects of the projected

process. Understanding the improvement of the ethnopedagogical culture of the future music teacher as an emerging phenomenon, teaching methods, on the one hand, stimulate the functional possibilities of general professional, ethnopedagogical and special knowledge, skills and abilities that students have. aimed at encouraging and facilitating the acquisition of new ones and their application in practice. Thus, in higher education, traditional teaching methods (explanatory and illustrative, reproductive, problem presentation, partial search, research), contextual educational methods (business, ethno composition of the population, characteristics, customs and traditions methods, project method) and methods of music pedagogy (teaching methods, creative tasks, thinking about music, the method of pedagogical foundations of the analysis of a musical work, performance methods, methods of musical literacy, listening, singing, listening, etc.).

The method of improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of the future music teacher was determined by three levels of its development (high, medium, low). The content of each of these levels depends on the improvement of the components of the ethnopedagogical culture of the music teacher (ethnopedagogical consciousness, ethnopedagogical thinking, ethnopedagogical activity). The criteria for improving ethnopedagogical culture of future music teachers are interest in Uzbek folk music pedagogy, emotional sensitivity of future music teachers to works of Uzbek folk music, the need to study folklore sources. is a feature that allows you to speak; awareness-the level of awareness about the ethnic origin of the person, understanding the educational essence of Uzbek folk pedagogy; direction of thinking-characteristics of the level of ethno-pedagogical knowledge, the ability to maintain and implement personal positions, creative abilities of the future music teacher; activation - the description of the frequency of reference to regional ethnopedagogical culture and the works of Uzbek folk pedagogy in general, as well as the level of formation of independent ethnopedagogical activity skills were found to be related. The effectiveness of the methodology for improving the ethno-pedagogical culture of the future music teacher was ensured by the following conditions: implementation of the principle of interdisciplinary integration; actualization of students' personal meanings in the ethno-pedagogical content material using person-oriented pedagogical situations; observing the relationship between the theoretical and practical preparation of students of the bachelor's degree in music education; one of them is the use of regional peculiarities of folk musical and pedagogical traditions.

In order to diagnose the initial state and dynamics of the formation of the professional culture of future music teachers in the course of instrumental and performance training, a diagnostic set was created that provides a comprehensive assessment of the formation of the components of the professional culture of students.

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